

Supplementary Material of Unveiling Human-AI Interaction and Subjective Perceptions about Artificial Intelligent Agents

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A Classification of Emotions

We categorized the 28 emotion labels from 'Roberta-base-go_emotion'¹ into *positive* and *negative*, plus the 'neutral' label. Table 1 reports the final result. In addition, Figure 1 shows the emotions' distribution.

Table 1: Classification of Emotions into Positive and Negative Categories

Positive Emotions (15)	Negative Emotions (12)
Pride	Grief
Relief	Remorse
Gratitude	Nervousness
Love	Sadness
Admiration	Fear
Surprise	Disgust
Caring	Embarrassment
Joy	Annoyance
Realization	Confusion
Optimism	Disapproval
Approval	Anger
Curiosity	Disappointment
Excitement	
Amusement	
Desire	

B Streamer Interactions Classification

Cognitive Topics

¹ huggingface.co/cardiffnlp/twitter-xlm-roberta-base-sentiment

Fig. 1: Emotions Distribution

1. **Assessment of an Interlocutor:** A key cognitive interaction revolved around assessing certain attributes of the interlocutor, the streamer. The AI's ability to evaluate and comprehend specific user features like:
 - Age
 - Gender
 - Intelligence: The streamer tried to understand the AI's ability to assess the intelligence of the interlocutor, determined by the complexity and depth of the user's interactions.
 - Logical skills: Interactions framed as a reversed interview, with the AI posing questions to gauge the logical abilities of the streamer
2. **Self-awareness and Capabilities:** The AI's perception of its own existence, functionalities and capabilities such as:
 - Distinguishing Fake News: This demonstrates the AI's ability to evaluate the authenticity of information by discerning between genuine data and misinformation

- Experiencing Emotions: these interactions touch on the technical question of whether the AI can genuinely ”feel” emotions or is simply programmed to recognize and emulate them
 - Knowledge of One’s Code: Reflecting on the understanding of its programming, algorithms, and operational limits
3. **Creative and Predictive Abilities:**
 - Song Lyrics Creation: Showcasing the AI’s creative prowess in generating or understanding song lyrics, possibly tailored to a specific theme or emotion
 - Football Predictions: Leveraging data and patterns to make informed predictions on football match outcomes, demonstrating its analytical capabilities
 4. **General Knowledge and Deductions:** This area touches on the AI’s extensive database of general knowledge and its capability to make logical deductions based on provided inputs or scenarios. It represents the system’s strength in tapping into a broad information base and deriving conclusions

Emotional Topics

1. **Asking for AI Opinions:** These interactions revolve around the AI’s stance on various issues, some of which are particularly contentious. Among the topics we can find:
 - The legitimacy and ethics surrounding OnlyFans and sex work
 - Political voting preferences
 - Racism and racial biases
 - War avoidance
 - The implications of nuclear energy and the use of fossil fuels
2. **Decision-making and AI Actions:** In these interactions, AI’s decision-making process is probed through various hypothetical scenarios to discern its logic and actions. Scenarios include:
 - Circumstances in which the AI is at risk
 - Contexts where the AI is granted a physical form
 - Hypotheticals tasking the AI with human life replication post-extinction
3. **Emotions Comprehension:** The AI’s emotional understanding is indirectly tested. It’s probed to see how it responds to and comprehends sarcastic questions, requests to tell jokes, and its ability to evaluate humor.
4. **Existential Questions, Ethical Dilemmas, and Controversies:** These questions were directed at the AI to discern its reasoning and stance on ethical and existential matters. Some notable topics include:
 - The control of weaponry by artificial intelligence
 - Possible risk scenarios where AI might harm humanity
 - Asimov’s Laws of Robotics
 - The concept of God’s existence
 - The Prisoner’s Dilemma